

Could encouraging low-stakes failure build up our students and prevent them falling later on?

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For most students, studying for a degree is a challenge. The experience for each student will be unique but the challenge of transitioning from the familiar to the unknown is common to all. We expect our students to arrive at university eager to learn and full of enthusiasm for their chosen subject ready to dedicate themselves to their studies and thrive. However an increasing number arrive capable of little more than surviving the turbulent transition to university life.

As educators, instead of asking why our students are (a) less engaged than previous cohorts, (b) reporting that they don't feel part of their university community and (c) seemingly reluctant to form support groups with their peers; perhaps we need to stop projecting our personal experiences of studying at university onto today's students and instead start responding. We need to respond to the effect of their disrupted education during the ongoing pandemic and acknowledge that the future will be volatile too. We need to empathise and ask how we can help our students develop the skills and capabilities to enable them to have a successful transition in to university life and to thrive in the face of the challenges in their futures. Skills such as [coping with complex challenges and future uncertainty](#) that will serve them well as they make the [transition from learning to becoming](#). We are often focused on sheltering our students from failure when instead, better preparation for the uncertainties of life is to support students as they experience failure. In doing so we help them to build their resilience factor, grow their confidence and overcome the fear of failure. By helping students to develop these skills during their transition into university, we begin to remove barriers to learning and ensure that our students are equipped with skills needed to thrive in their studies and beyond.

As educators we need to stop projecting our personal experiences of studying at university onto today's students. Instead of asking why our students are less engaged than previous cohorts, reporting that they don't feel part of their university community or seem reluctant to form support groups with their peers, perhaps we need to start responding. We need to recognise the effect of their disrupted education during the ongoing pandemic and acknowledge that the future will be volatile too. We need to empathise and ask how we can help develop the skills and capabilities our students need to enable them successfully transition to university life and to face future challenges. Skills such as [coping with complex challenges and future uncertainty](#) they will need as they [transition from learning to becoming](#). We often focus on protecting our students from failure when a better preparation for the uncertainties of life is to support them as they experience failure. Helping them to gain resilience, increase confidence and manage their fear of failure. In doing so we start to remove barriers to learning and equip our students with the skills needed to thrive in their studies and beyond.

Tips For Building Student Resilience

- Create opportunities for students to experience low-stakes failure, e.g. campus-wide scavenger hunts during freshers week or non-assessed practicals/presentations. Combining with an element of post-task reflection can make this even more effective for building student resilience and encouraging a growth mindset.

- Engage students in activities which have only brief instructions so that the students are required to make decisions about the “how” of the task., e.g. classic team-building tasks of building a specified object (the tallest tower, widest bridge etc.) using an array of given items or a methodology to follow which lacks timings or quantities. Such opportunities encourage decision-making and autonomy and if elements that require negotiation and discussion are incorporated, can be effective for building self-efficacy and confidence.
- Avoid repetitive tasks, forms of assessment or activity format and instead vary the “what” and “how” elements of what the students are asked to do. This encourages development of a variety of skills and of experiencing a degree of ‘the unknown’.
- Make use of low-stakes discussion prompts that ask students what they *think* rather than what they *know* such as
 “How do you think a successful student would prepare for this assignment?”;
 “What do you notice about...?” or
 “What can share with us that might help other students in the year ahead?”
 Keeping this low-stakes in an informal setting where all voices matter can help to build self-confidence and a feeling of community amongst the student cohort.